

SYNHARMONIC VARIANTS AND PARALLELS

**G.Rayeva, Candidate of Philological Sciences,
Kazakh State Pedagogical University named after Abay,
E.O‘rinboyeva, FarDU katta o‘qituvchisi (PhD)**

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada turkiy tillarga xos fonetik hodisalar, jumladan, singarmonistik variant va parallelizmlar haqida ilmiy-nazariy qarashlar hamda muallif xulosalari berilgan. Tillarning uzluksiz rivojlanishi natijasida orqa va o‘rta til unlilari va undoshlari tilning old qismiga o‘tganligi, buning sabablari, qadimgi turkiy davrlarda yumshoq talaffuz qilinadigan so‘zlar mutlaqo bo‘lmaganligi, ularning faqat qattiq versiyalari ishlatilganligi turkiy (jumladan, qozoq) tillar misolida tahlilga tortilgan.*

Abstract. *This article presents scientific and theoretical views on phonetic phenomena specific to Turkic languages, including synharmonic variants and parallelisms, as well as the author's conclusions. The reasons for this, the complete absence of soft-pronounced words in ancient Turkic times, and the use of only hard versions of them, are analyzed using the example of Turkic (including Kazakh) languages.*

Аннотация. *В статье изложены научно-теоретические взгляды и выводы автора относительно фонетических явлений, характерных для тюркских языков, в том числе сингармонических вариантов и параллелизмов. На примере тюркских (в том числе казахского) языков проанализирована причина этого, а именно тот факт, что в результате непрерывного развития языков задне- и среднеподъязычные гласные и согласные переместились в переднюю часть языка, поскольку в древнетюркские времена совершенно не существовало слов с мягким произношением, а использовались только их твердые варианты.*

Kalit so‘z va iboralar: *turkiy tillar, unlilar uyg‘unligi, tarixiy muvofiqlik, variantlar, unlilar, undoshlar.*

Keywords: *turkic languages, synharmonism, historic compliance, variants, vowels, consonants.*

Ключевые слова: *тюркские языки, гармония гласных, историческая гармония, варианты, гласные, согласные.*

Tunguzo-manjurian, mongolian, turkic, (in a broad sense – languages of the ural-altaic family) languages had experienced polysynthetic or amorphous state before they became agglutinative. In its earliest form the language underwent destruction because of unknown reasons but later it was restored having saved generic semantics of a word, there appeared a law of synharmonism. Among Altaic languages the synharmonism is well-preserved in Turkic languages. Phonetic, phonomorphologic structure of words is different in various languages. The only characteristic feature for Turkic languages – harmony of vowels. Synharmonism as a fundamental structural typological phenomenon joins sounds into one whole unit. It differentiates words in the stream of speech, at the same time it serves as a word-formation element . In a case of synharmonism a special role is given to vowels as

they together with a consonant form a syllable, define their common nature. As a result of the latest achievements in linguistics synharmonism is considered to be not only as the harmony of vowels but also as a united phonetic complexity of a vowel and a consonant in the structure of a word. In modern Turkic languages synharmonism is manifested in two kinds: backlingual vowels are in harmony with backlingual vowels, forelingual vowels are in harmony with forelingual vowels. This is called palatal harmony. But there are cases when labial vowels of the root syllable govern non-labial vowels in the following syllables making them similar to itself. This case is called labial harmony. In the process of research various methods are used: descriptive including the study of the factual material, generalization, interpretation, comparative historical analysis (research of Turkic languages, dialects and ancient turkic writings). Such a composite approach allowed us to carry out a systematic study of synharmonic variants and parallels in the Kazakh language.

In Turkic languages among them in a lexical structure of Kazakh there are fairly good number of words that do not observe the basic law of synharmonism even with the presence of a common adequate lexical meaning of a root. They are pronounced as different vowels: either forelingual, backlingual or open and narrow. Besides they form various kinds of equivalents. For example, a-ï darïlda~ dïpïlda (cry, shout), a-e kauak ~ keuek (empty, vacant), a- ä ajïm ~ ajim (wrinkles); o-ö doŋgala ~ döŋgele (round) . Root vowels of monosemantic parallel words are alternated between themselves not only in a literary language but also in local dialects. For example, ojar-ojir (insolent, rude), kajar ~ kajïr (strength, persistence, energy), arkali ~ arkïli (across, along) [3, 12-46]. Equivalents of vowels formed by alteration free from the law of synharmonism are met in other Turkic languages by a comparative study of them. For example, in a Bashkirian language: a-ä asï ~ äse (bitter, sour), as ~ äs (quietly, slowly), akïrïn ~ äkiren (few, little) [5, 143-144]. A hard form of a word “äje” meaning “grandmother, mother, father’s mother” has the form “aja”. The latter is met in a proverb “Ai der aja jok” (There’s no senior to say “hey!”, no master to say “leave it”). In the poem “Khibatul Khakaik” there is a line “igit koja bolur” . The old “koja” in ancient turkic meant “an old person, man”. Taking into consideration the fact that our ancestors recognized elder people as heads of a community it comes out that any elderly person in a house is considered to be a master with full rights and full power. Possibly the word in the meaning “ruler of the country, lord” was used at that time in reference to the head of a religious commune arriving from arabian countries. In a proverb “Ai der aja jok, koi der koja jok” a word “koja” functions in the meaning “ata” (grandfather), a word “aja” in the meaning “äje” (grandmother). “Aja” has the same root of the word “ajïm” (wrinkles on the face). “Ajïm” remained in local dialects of a conversational speech, in a bookish language as “äjim”. Probably the word “aja” derived from grandmother’s wrinkled face. Words “aja” and “äje” are considered to be variants of one and the same word.

As follows from the above a hard variant of a word was used parallelly with its soft variant, and then with the period of time the latter variant was gradually forced out of the use. The above-mentioned examples allow us to observe the fact that alternation of open, narrow, forelingual and backlingual vowels in the root of

definite words free from the law of synharmonism is the historic phenomenon embracing all Turkic languages. But word variations are not always adequate. Among them we all encounter words having various semantic differences or words that had acquired some stylistic functional shades. For example: apat-opat. Apat - “disaster, spontaneous disaster, accident”; opat - “die”. The word “apat” expresses the notion about the future or present events, whereas the word “opat” expresses the notion about past, completed events. Tat-tot. Tat – “rust”; tot “oxide”, tan (tot basu – to be covered with rust)”. One of the words show the process of the action, another – the result of the action.

M.L.Cherkasskiy suggests to call monosemantic words as “synharmonic variants”: parallel roots slightly differing from each other in their meaning as “synharmonic parallels” [2, 69-70]. M. Mollova gives the following proof of the discrepancy of the term between its content and meaning: “Spontaneous transition i.e. the equivalence of one of phoneme to the other is a phonetic phenomenon. Alternation of vowels in words without any phonological meaningful load is historic phenomenon. Owing to this the given term is unsuccessful, it cannot embrace the meaning of words in full [6,59]. M.L. Cherkasskiy gives the following opinion about synharmonic variants and parallels Turkic languages had polysynthetic structure before they turned to be agglutinative in ancient altaic epoch. According to the polysynthetic structure separate words are joined into complexity which is submitted to the law of synharmonism.

On account of vowels having carried no phonological load their pronunciation depended on consonants. Because of this qualitative alteration of vowel sounds have arisen. Therefore synharmonic variants and parallels produce the relic remained in the process of evolutionary development of Turkic language structure.

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